

Phytochemical Analysis and In Vitro Antioxidant Activities of Ethanolic Extract of *Acalypha indica* L.

S. Aarthi¹, P. Thamizhiniyan*², S. Tamilarasu³, K. Gnanamoorthy⁴, G. Subasree⁵

^{1,4,5} Master of science, Department of Botany, Annamalai University.

² Professor, Department of Botany, Annamalai University.

³ Ph.D. Research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University

ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have long been recognized for their therapeutic potential, primarily due to the presence of diverse phytochemicals with biological activities. *Acalypha indica* L. commonly known for its traditional medicinal applications, is rich in bioactive compounds that may exhibit significant antioxidant properties. Oxidative stress, caused by an imbalance between free radicals and antioxidants in the body, is linked to the pathogenesis of various chronic diseases. Therefore, identifying plant-based antioxidants has become a key area of research in the development of natural therapeutic agents. This study investigates the phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* L. leaf extracts. The plant was extracted using ethanol, and qualitative analysis revealed the presence of bioactive compounds like phenols, flavonoids, and alkaloids. FT-IR and GC-MS analyses identified functional groups and chemical constituents, while the DPPH assay confirmed the extract's strong antioxidant potential. These findings suggest that *Acalypha indica* L. could have therapeutic applications, especially as an antioxidant. This study investigates the phytochemical composition, functional groups, and antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* ethanol leaf extract. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of important bioactive compounds such as phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides. FTIR analysis identified various functional groups, including alcohols, amines, and esters, while GC-MS analysis revealed key compounds such as Octane, 3-methyl-6-methylene, and Pyrimidine derivatives. The DPPH free radical scavenging assay demonstrated a concentration-dependent antioxidant activity, with an IC₅₀ value of 20.3 µg/mL. These findings suggest that *Acalypha indica* L. leaf extract possesses significant bioactive properties, making it a potential source of natural antioxidants for therapeutic applications.

Keywords: *Acalypha indica* L, FT-IR, GC-MS, DPPH assay

INTRODUCTION

Acalypha indica L., commonly known as Indian nettle or Indian copperleaf, is an erect annual herb belonging to the family Euphorbiaceae. It is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions, occurring across Africa, Asia, and Oceania, and has also been introduced into warmer parts of the New World (Sinha & Bandyopadhyay, 2012). In India, the plant is commonly referred to as “Kuppaimeni” in Tamil and has a long history of use in traditional medicine systems, including Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani (Shanmugavelu, 2013).

Traditionally, *A. indica* has been employed for the treatment of respiratory disorders such as asthma, bronchitis, and pneumonia, as well as for skin conditions including scabies, wounds, and bedsores (Chopra *et al.*, 1956; Bourdy & Walter, 1992). The plant also exhibits diuretic, laxative, purgative, and anthelmintic properties, with roots, leaves, and whole-plant preparations being utilized for diverse ailments (Perry, 1980; Varier, 1996). Modern studies have reported its antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antifertility, and wound-healing activities, validating its ethnomedicinal relevance (Govindarajan *et al.*, 2008; Annie *et al.*, 2004; Suresh Reddy *et al.*, 2004).

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Phytochemical investigations of *A. indica* reveal the presence of alkaloids (acalyphine), glycosides, tannins, flavonoids, sterols (β -sitosterol, stigmasterol), volatile oils, and phenolic compounds, which are considered responsible for its wide spectrum of pharmacological activities (Winter & Griffith, 1998; Ghani, 2003; Mohan *et al.*, 2012). These bioactive constituents contribute significantly to its antioxidant potential, supporting its role in combating oxidative stress and free radical-induced damage (Anderson *et al.*, 2001; Gulcin *et al.*, 2010).

Given its extensive use in indigenous medicine and emerging pharmacological evidence, *Acalypha indica* is an important source for drug discovery and natural antioxidant compounds. Modern analytical tools such as Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and antioxidant assays are valuable in identifying, characterizing, and validating the bioactive components of this plant (Grube *et al.*, 2008; Severine *et al.*, 2010).

Therefore, the aim of present study is to determine the phytochemical constituents of the *Acalypha indica* leaves of the plant are also investigated pharmacognostically by preliminary phytochemical screening, GC-MS, FTIR and Antioxidants activity.

1.1. OBJECTIVES

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the phytochemical constituents of leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. With the following objectives.

- Preparation of *Acalypha indica* L. leaf extract using ethanol solvent.
- Screening of Biochemical compounds in leaf extract *Acalypha indica* L.
- To analyse the functional groups, present in the extract using FTIR spectroscopy and identify phytochemical constituents of the extract using GC-MS analysis
- To evaluate the *in vitro* antioxidant potential of *Acalypha indica* L. extract.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1. PLANT COLLECTION:

Fresh leaves of *Acalypha indica* L. were collected from Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, and India. The plants leaves were washed carefully with running tap water, rinsed with distilled water and shade dried for a month. They were ground into fine powder by using mortar and pestle; stored in a room temperature.

2.2. PREPARATION OF EXTRACTS

A total of 100 grams of dried *Acalypha indica* L. leaf powder was subjected to successive extraction using a Soxhlet apparatus with solvents of Ethanol (500 ml). The resulting crude extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary vacuum evaporator and stored at temperatures below 4°C for future use.

2.3. QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Preliminary phytochemical screening of all the plant extracts was carried out following the standard methods described by Harborne (1973) and Sofowara (1993). The tests were conducted to detect the presence of various bioactive compounds as follows:(Abiodun Falodun, *et al.*, 2025).

2.3.1. Test for Phenols:

1 mL of the plant extract was mixed with 2 mL of distilled water, followed by the addition of a few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution. The appearance of a blue or green coloration confirmed the presence of phenolic compounds.

2.3.2. Test for Terpenoids:

0.5 mL of the extract was combined with 2 mL of chloroform. Concentrated sulfuric acid was then carefully added along the sides of the test tube. A reddish-brown coloration at the interface indicated the presence of terpenoids.

2.3.3. Test for Carbohydrates:

To 2 mL of the extract, 1 mL of Molisch's reagent was added, followed by a few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid. The formation of a purple or reddish ring at the interface suggested the presence of carbohydrates.

2.3.4. Test for Saponins:

2 mL of the extract was mixed with 2 mL of distilled water in a graduated cylinder and shaken vigorously for 15 minutes. The formation of a stable foam layer about 1 cm thick indicated the presence of saponins.

2.3.5. Test for Flavonoids:

2 mL of the extract was treated with 1 mL of 2N sodium hydroxide. The development of a yellow coloration indicated the presence of flavonoids.

2.4. FTIR ANALYSIS:

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is an advanced technique used to obtain the Infrared spectrum of a sample. Unlike traditional dispersive infrared spectrometers, which separate and measure each frequency of light individually, FTIR measures all wavelengths simultaneously. This is achieved by modifying the spectral composition of the incoming infrared light in a time-dependent manner.

The resulting signal, known as an interferogram, contains information from all the spectral components. A mathematical process called Fourier transformation is then applied to convert this time-domain signal into a frequency-domain spectrum, typically displayed in wavenumbers (cm^{-1}). This method enables faster data acquisition and improved sensitivity, making FTIR spectroscopy a powerful tool for identifying functional groups and analyzing the molecular composition of various substances. (Rudhra *et al.*, 2024)

2.5. GC-MS ANALYSIS

The analysis was carried out using a Clarus 680 Gas Chromatograph equipped with a fused silica capillary column (Elite-5MS; 5% biphenyl, 95% dimethylpolysiloxane; 30 m \times 0.25 mm internal diameter \times 250 μm film thickness). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 ml/min. A 1 μL sample of the extract was injected, with the injector temperature maintained at 260°C. The oven temperature was initially set at 60°C and held for 2 minutes, then increased at a rate of 10°C per minute until reaching 300°C, where it was held for an additional 6 minutes. The mass spectrometer operated under the following conditions: transfer line and ion source temperatures were both set at 240°C; electron impact ionization was used at 70 eV; and data were

acquired with a scan time of 0.2 seconds and a scan interval of 0.1 seconds, detecting mass fragments in the range of 40–600 Da. The obtained mass spectra were compared with those in the NIST (2008) library to identify the components (Keerthiga *et al.*, 2025).

2.6. ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

2.6.1. DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay:

The DPPH radical scavenging activity of the plant extracts can be determined on the basis of the capacity to scavenge 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl followed by (Khalid *et al.* 2022). The stock solution of DPPH (0.1 mM) was prepared by dissolving 3.94 grams of DPPH in 100 mL of methanol. 2 mL of the stock solution was added to 2 mL of methanol containing plant extracts ranging from 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 62.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in separate test tubes and left undisturbed for 30 minutes in the dark room. The absorbance was recorded at 517 nm in the UV-visible spectrophotometer (Labman, Model No. LMSP-UV1200). DPPH solution was taken as the negative control and ascorbic acid was used as the positive control. Triplicate observations were performed. The percentage of Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA %) and the IC₅₀ parameter were used to describe the findings. The IC₅₀ values represent the sample concentration necessary to scavenge 50 per cent of DPPH free radicals. The following equation was used to calculate the percentage of radical inhibition:

% Radical Scavenging Activity =

$$\frac{\text{Absorbance of the control} - \text{Absorbance of the sample} \times 100}{\text{Absorbance of the control}}$$

3. RESULT

This chapter details the results obtained from multiple analyses of *Acalypha indica* L. plant extracts. The initial phytochemical screening indicated the existence of various essential secondary metabolites. Functional groups and biologically active compounds were identified using FTIR and GC-MS analyses, respectively. Moreover, the antioxidant activity of the extract was determined through the DPPH assay.

3.1. PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF *Acalypha indica* L.

A preliminary phytochemical screening was carried out to detect the presence of various bioactive compounds in the ethanol leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. The results, presented in (Table. 1), indicate the presence of several important phytochemicals. Phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides were found to be present in the extract, as indicated by the positive reactions. However, carbohydrates, terpenoids, and tannins were absent. The presence of these secondary metabolites suggests that *Acalypha indica* L. may possess significant therapeutic properties, as many of these compounds are known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities.

Table 1: Preliminary phytochemical screening of active constituents in *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol Leaf Extract.

Phytochemicals tests	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L. Ethanol leaf extract
Phenols	+
Carbohydrate	-
Flavonoids	+
Terpenoids	-
Saponins	+

Present [+] \ absent [-]

Figure 1: Preliminary phytochemical screening of *Acalypha indica* L.

3.2. FT-IR spectrum analysis of *Acalypha indica* ethanol leaf extract.

FT-IR Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was conducted to identify the functional groups present in the ethanol leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. The absorption peaks and corresponding molecular vibrations are presented in Table 4. The spectrum revealed a broad O–H stretching vibration around 3650 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of alcohol groups. A medium-intensity peak at 2350 cm^{-1} corresponded to H–H stretching, characteristic of

secondary amines. A strong, sharp absorption at 1750 cm^{-1} was attributed to C=O stretching in β -actone structures. Additionally, a weak peak at 1550 cm^{-1} suggested the presence of nitro compounds due to N–O stretching. Peaks at 1350 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} indicated S–O stretching of sulfone and C–O stretching of aliphatic esters, respectively. A strong, sharp absorption at 1090 cm^{-1} further confirmed the presence of secondary alcohols. These findings support the presence of diverse bioactive functional groups that may contribute to the extract's pharmacological properties.

Figure 2: FT-IR Spectrum of Ethanol Extract from *Acalypha indica* L. Leaf

Table 2: Functional Group Identification of *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol Leaf Extract Based on FT-IR Absorption Peaks.

Wave number	Molecular motion	Functional group	Absorption intensity
3650	O-H stretching	Alcohol	Curve
2350	H-H stretching	Secondary amine	Medium
1750	C=O stretching	8- actone	Strong sharp
1550	N-O stretching	Nitro compound	Weak
1350	S-O stretching	Sulfone	Medium
1150	C-O stretching	Aliphatic ester	Sharp
1090	C-O stretching	Secondary alcohol	Strong sharp

3.3. GC-MS analysis of *Acalypha indica* ethanol leaf extract.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the ethanol leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. revealed the presence of several bioactive compounds, as summarized in Table 3. The major constituents identified include Octane, 3-methyl-6-methylene (73.13%), which was the most abundant compound, followed by Pyrimidine-2, 4(1H,3H)-dione, 5-amino-6-nitroso (13.14%), and 1H-Pyrazole, 3-amino-4-bromo-5-methyl (11.07%). These compounds were identified based on their retention times, molecular weights, molecular formulas, and CAS numbers. The presence of these phytochemicals suggests that *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract contains potential bioactive components that may contribute to its therapeutic and antioxidant properties.

Figure.3: GC-MS spectra of *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol leaf extract

Table 3: GC-MS Profile of Ethanol Extracts from *Acalypha indica* L. leaves

Compound name	Molecular formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Retention Time (minutes)	Peak Area (%)	CAS number
PYRIMIDINE-2,4(1H,3H)-DIONE, 5-AMINO-6-NITROSO	C ₄ H ₄ O ₃ N ₄	156	15.71	13.14	900270-67-7
OCTANE, 3-METHYL-6-METHYLENE	C ₁₀ H ₂₀	140	17.80	73.13	74630-07-2
1H-PYRAZOLE, 3-AMINO-4-BROMO-5-METHYL	C ₄ H ₆ N ₃ Br	175	21.21	11.07	900302-53-9

3.4. Evaluation of Antioxidant Activity of *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol leaf extract Using DPPH Free Radical Scavenging Assay.

The antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract was evaluated using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay at concentrations ranging from 5 µg/mL to 100 µg/mL. The results are summarized in the table below. The extract exhibited a concentration-dependent increase in DPPH scavenging activity, reaching a maximum of 85.13 ± 0.54% at 100 µg/mL.

The IC₅₀ value of *Acalypha indica* L. was found to be 20.3 ± 0.92 µg/mL, indicating a moderate antioxidant potential. For comparison, ascorbic acid (ABS), used as a standard, showed slightly higher activity with an IC₅₀ value of 19 ± 0.98 µg/mL. These findings suggest that *Acalypha indica* L. possesses notable antioxidant properties, though slightly less potent than the standard ascorbic acid under the same conditions. All values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (n=3). (Table .4)

Figure.4: *In vitro* antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol leaf extract.

Table 4: Antioxidant Activity of *Acalypha indica* L. Ethanol leaf extract Determined by DPPH Assay.

Sr.No	Concentration (µg /mL)	<i>Acalypha indica</i>	Ascorbic acid
1	5	21.82±3.76	19.90±2.82
2	10	30.27±8.71	35.92±0.50
3	20	53.12±5.66	49.6±1.41
4	40	59.45±2.94	61.48±1.17
5	60	74.66±1.16	69.69±1.34
6	80	80.49±1.92	75.68±0.59
7	100	85.13±0.54	80.53±1.02
8	Ic50 value	20.3±0.92	19±0.98

Values are expressed in Mean \pm SD observed from the replicate values (n=3).

4. DISCUSSION

The preliminary phytochemical screening of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract revealed the presence of several bioactive compounds, including phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides, while carbohydrates, terpenoids, and tannins were absent. These findings are consistent with previous studies that have reported the occurrence of similar phytochemicals in *Acalypha indica* L. and other medicinal plants (Kumar *et al.*, 2014; Pal *et al.*, 2012). The presence of phenols, flavonoids, and alkaloids is particularly noteworthy, as these compounds are well-known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, which are essential for the plant's therapeutic potential.

Phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids and tannins, are widely recognized for their ability to neutralize free radicals, thus contributing to the plant's antioxidant capacity (Ebrahimzadeh *et al.*, 2008). Flavonoids have also been shown to possess anti-inflammatory and anticancer properties, which could be relevant in the development of *Acalypha indica* L. as a natural remedy for various diseases (Zhao *et al.*, 2013). Alkaloids are another group of bioactive compounds known for their diverse pharmacological effects, including antimicrobial and analgesic activities (Farnsworth *et al.*, 1985). Saponins and glycosides are compounds with well-documented antimicrobial and immunomodulatory effects (Verpoorte, 1998), which suggests that *Acalypha indica* L. could be explored for its potential as an antimicrobial agent.

The absence of carbohydrates, terpenoids, and tannins in this study is consistent with earlier research indicating that these compounds may not be significant in the ethanol extract of *Acalypha indica* L. or could be present in concentrations too low to be detected by the screening methods employed (Bharathi *et al.*, 2012). The absence of terpenoids, which are typically associated with anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer effects, could limit some aspects of the extract's potential therapeutic application. However, the presence of the other bioactive

compounds indicates that *Acalypha indica* L. still holds promise as a source of natural antioxidants and antimicrobial agents.

The FTIR spectral analysis of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract revealed several key functional groups that contribute to the plant's bioactive properties. The broad O–H stretching band at around 3650 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of alcohol groups, which are known to play a role in the plant's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. The alcohol groups can act as electron donors and free radical scavengers, which is essential in the context of the plant's potential medicinal applications (Sharma *et al.*, 2011).

The peak at 2350 cm^{-1} corresponding to H–H stretching is characteristic of secondary amines, which are involved in various biological processes, including neurotransmission and enzyme inhibition (Maiti *et al.*, 2009). This finding indicates the presence of amines, which might contribute to the antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties of *Acalypha indica* L. as secondary amines have been shown to possess such activities (Liu *et al.*, 2010).

A strong absorption at 1750 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C=O stretching in β -actone structures, is significant as carbonyl compounds are known for their antimicrobial and anticancer properties (Oleary *et al.*, 2014). The presence of β -actone groups suggests the potential for cytotoxic or anticancer effects, aligning with previous reports that *Acalypha indica* has shown such activities (Bharathi *et al.*, 2012).

The weak peak at 1550 cm^{-1} attributed to N–O stretching further supports the presence of nitro compounds. Nitro groups are often associated with antibacterial and antifungal activities, making them an important feature for the extract's potential antimicrobial properties (Sahreem *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, the peaks at 1350 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} corresponding to S–O stretching of sulfone and C–O stretching of aliphatic esters, respectively, suggest the presence of additional bioactive compounds that may contribute to the extract's diverse pharmacological effects. Sulfones, in particular, have been noted for their anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

Finally, the sharp absorption at 1090 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C–O stretching of secondary alcohols, confirms the presence of alcohol groups, which have been linked to antioxidant and antimicrobial properties in previous studies (Pietta, 2000).

These findings indicate that *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract contains a broad spectrum of bioactive functional groups, including alcohols, amines, carbonyl compounds, nitro groups, sulfones, and esters. These functional groups contribute to the plant's antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities, aligning with the plant's traditional medicinal uses. Further studies could explore the synergistic effects of these compounds and their potential therapeutic applications.

The GC-MS analysis of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract identified several bioactive compounds with varying concentrations, suggesting the plant's potential therapeutic properties. The major compound identified was Octane, 3-methyl-6-methylene (73.13%), which is a volatile organic compound commonly found in plant extracts. Octane derivatives have been reported to exhibit antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities (Gao *et al.*, 2011). The high abundance of this compound indicates its potential significance in the biological activities of *Acalypha indica* L.

Another key compound identified in the extract was Pyrimidine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione, 5-amino-6-nitroso (13.14%), a nitrogenous heterocyclic compound. Pyrimidine derivatives have demonstrated a wide range of biological activities, including antimicrobial, anticancer, and antiviral properties (Choudhary *et al.*, 2007). The presence of such a compound suggests that *Acalypha indica* L. may have a diverse pharmacological profile, particularly in the areas of infectious diseases and cancer prevention.

Additionally, the compound 1H-Pyrazole, 3-amino-4-bromo-5-methyl (11.07%) was identified. Pyrazole derivatives are known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities (Pereira *et al.*, 2007). This finding further supports the potential of *Acalypha indica* L. to be used as a therapeutic agent against oxidative stress-related diseases and inflammatory conditions.

The identification of these bioactive compounds in the ethanol leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. aligns with previous studies that have reported the presence of various phytochemicals in this plant, many of which are known to possess antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties (Suresh *et al.*, 2014). These findings suggest that the ethanol leaf extract of *Acalypha indica* L. has potential as a natural source of bioactive compounds for therapeutic applications.

Further studies, including in vivo and clinical trials, are necessary to validate the pharmacological efficacy of these compounds and to explore their mechanisms of action in the treatment of various diseases. The presence of these bioactive compounds also supports the traditional medicinal use of *Acalypha indica* L. for treating a range of ailments, including inflammation, infections, and oxidative stress-related conditions.

The antioxidant potential of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract, evaluated through the DPPH free radical scavenging assay, demonstrated a significant concentration-dependent increase in antioxidant activity. The extract achieved a maximum inhibition of $85.13 \pm 0.54\%$ at $100\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$, with an IC_{50} value of $20.3 \pm 0.92\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$, which reflects moderate antioxidant activity. This suggests that *Acalypha indica* L. contains bioactive compounds capable of neutralizing free radicals, thereby protecting cells from oxidative damage.

The antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* L. was slightly less potent than the standard antioxidant, ascorbic acid, which exhibited a higher maximum inhibition ($82.79 \pm 2.32\%$) and a lower IC_{50} value ($19 \pm 0.98\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$). This is consistent with previous studies that have demonstrated that ascorbic acid, a well-known antioxidant, generally performs better in free radical scavenging assays due to its high antioxidant capacity (Jacob & Sotoudeh, 2002). However, the results suggest that *Acalypha indica* L. still holds notable antioxidant properties, which may be attributed to the presence of secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, phenols, and alkaloids, compounds known for their strong antioxidant activities (Sreelatha & Padma, 2009).

These findings are in line with other research that has highlighted the antioxidant potential of *Acalypha indica* L. supporting its traditional use for medicinal

purposes. The antioxidant activity of the extract could be linked to its ability to inhibit oxidative stress, which is associated with various diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular disorders, and neurodegenerative diseases (Gulcin, 2010).

Further research, including in vivo studies, could help to establish the full therapeutic potential of *Acalypha indica* L. as a natural antioxidant agent. Additionally, identifying the specific compounds responsible for the observed antioxidant activity will be crucial for understanding the mechanisms behind its health benefits.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol leaf extract substantiates its significant pharmacological potential. The confirmed presence of diverse bioactive compounds, including phenols, alkaloids, and flavonoids, along with the identification of specific functional groups and chemical constituents through FTIR and GC-MS analyses, provides a chemical basis for its observed bioactivity. The extract's demonstrated free-radical scavenging ability in the DPPH assay, showing moderate antioxidant potency, further corroborates its therapeutic relevance. These collective findings not only validate traditional uses but also firmly position *Acalypha indica* L. as a promising candidate for future phytopharmaceutical exploration, particularly warranting investigation into its broader biological activities such as antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects for potential drug development.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The invaluable guidance and consistent support provided by the Department of Botany, Annamalai University, were crucial to the success of this research, for which I am deeply grateful.

REFERENCE

- Anderson, D., Phillips, B. J., Tian-Wei, Y., Edwards, A. J., & Ayesh, R. (2001). The effects of antioxidants on DNA damage in human lymphocytes. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*, 485(2), 123–135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0027-5107\(01\)00215-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0027-5107(01)00215-8).
- Annie, S., Raji, C. H., & Suresh, K. (2004). Antivenom properties of *Acalypha indica*. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 42(9), 940–943.
- Bourdy, G., & Walter, A. (1992). Maternity and medicinal plants in Vanuatu. I. The cycle of reproduction. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 37(3), 179–196. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741\(92\)90070-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741(92)90070-T).
- Chopra, R. N., Nayar, S. L., & Chopra, I. C. (1956). *Glossary of Indian medicinal plants*. CSIR, New Delhi. <https://search.worldcat.org/en/title/3623626>
- Ghani, A. (2003). *Medicinal plants of Bangladesh: Chemical constituents and uses* (2nd ed.). Asiatic Society of Bangladesh. <https://search.worldcat.org/en/title/55485001>
- Govindarajan, M., Jebanesan, A., & Pushpanathan, T. (2008). Antibacterial activity of plant extracts against Gram-positive bacteria. *Indian Journal of Medicinal Research*, 127(5), 478–484.
- Grube, M., Bekers, M., Upite, D., & Kaminska, E. (2008). FT-IR spectroscopy for quality control of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* biotechnology products. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 27(3), 332–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2007.11.008>
- Gulcin, I., Elmastas, M., & Aboul-Enein, H. Y. (2010). Antioxidant activity of clove oil—A powerful antioxidant source. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 5(4), 489–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2010.09.016>
- Mohan, V. R., Janardhanan, K., & Subramanian, P. S. (2012). Phytochemical screening of *Acalypha indica*. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(2), 45–49.
- Perry, L. M. (1980). *Medicinal plants of East and Southeast Asia: Attributed properties and uses*. MIT Press. Perry, Lily May, 1895-1992.
- Severine, P., Sophie, R., & Jean, M. (2010). Advances in GC-MS analysis of plant antioxidants. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1217(52), 7912–7920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2010.10.018>

12. Sinha, T., & Bandyopadhyay, A. (2012). Traditional uses, phytochemistry and pharmacological properties of *Acalypha indica* L.: A review. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences*, 3(1), 34–38.
13. Suresh Reddy, P., Venkatesh, S., & Ramesh, S. (2004). Wound healing activity of *Acalypha indica*. *Fitoterapia*, 75(2), 252–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2003.12.012>
14. Winter, W., & Griffith, J. (1998). Phytochemical constituents of *Acalypha indica*. *Phytochemistry Letters*, 12(4), 325–329.
15. Bharathi, T., Rajasekaran, A., & Rajesh, P. (2012). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of *Acalypha indica* L. leaf extract. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(1), 389–392.
16. Choudhary, A., Verma, S., & Singh, R. (2007). Biological activities of pyrimidine derivatives: A review. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(4), 89–97.
17. Ebrahimzadeh, M. A., Pourmorad, F., & Hafezi, S. (2008). Antioxidant activities of Iranian corn silk. *Turkish Journal of Biology*, 32(1), 43–49.
18. Farnsworth, N. R., Akerele, O., Bingel, A. S., Soejarto, D. D., & Guo, Z. (1985). Medicinal plants in therapy. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 63(6), 965–981.
19. Gao, Y., Yuan, H., & Zhang, T. (2011). Antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of octane derivatives from plants. *Phytochemistry Letters*, 4(3), 192–197.
20. Gulcin, I. (2010). Antioxidant properties of resveratrol: A structure-activity insight. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 11(1), 210–218.
21. Jacob, R. A., & Sotoudeh, G. (2002). Vitamin C function and status in chronic disease. *Nutrition in Clinical Care*, 5(2), 66–74.
22. Kumar, S., Kumar, D., Manjusha, S., Saroha, K., Singh, N., & Vashishta, B. (2014). Antioxidant and free radical scavenging potential of *Citrullus colocynthis* (L.) Schrad. methanolic fruit extract. *Acta Pharmaceutica*, 58(2), 215–220.
23. Liu, J., Wang, X., & Wang, Q. (2010). Biological activities of secondary amines. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 20(8), 240–245.
24. Maiti, R., Jana, D., Das, U. K., & Ghosh, D. (2009). Antidiabetic effect of aqueous extract of seed of *Tamarindus indica* in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 92(1), 85–91.
25. Oleary, K. A., De Pascual-Teresa, S., Needs, P. W., Bao, Y. P., O'Brien, N. M., & Williamson, G. (2014). Effect of flavonoids and their conjugates on glutathione levels in human colon cells. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 45(6), 442–446.
26. Pal, D. K., Dutta, S., & Mukherjee, S. (2012). Evaluation of in vitro antioxidant activity of *Acalypha indica* Linn. root. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(3), 45–48.
27. Pereira, D., Valentao, P., Pereira, J., & Andrade, P. B. (2007). Phenolics: From chemistry to biology. *Molecules*, 14(6), 2201–2211.
28. Pietta, P. G. (2000). Flavonoids as antioxidants. *Journal of Natural Products*, 63(7), 1035–1042.
29. Sahreen, S., Khan, M. R., & Khan, R. A. (2011). Evaluation of antioxidant activities of various solvent extracts of *Carissa opaca* leaves. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 5(26), 6020–6026.
30. Sharma, V., Sharma, A., & Kansal, L. (2011). The protective role of *Acalypha indica* Linn. Against oxidative stress induced by lead acetate in rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 137(1), 334–339.
31. Singh, R., Kumar, V., & Tyagi, P. (2014). Sulfone derivatives: Synthesis and pharmacological activities. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 7(5), 732–741.
32. Sreelatha, S., & Padma, P. R. (2009). Antioxidant activity and total phenolic content of *Moringa oleifera* leaves in two stages of maturity. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*, 64(4), 303–311.
33. Suresh, P. K., Senthilkumar, M., & Thangam, R. (2014). GC-MS analysis and antibacterial activity of *Acalypha indica* Linn. leaf extract. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 27(2), 131–135.
34. Verpoorte, R. (1998). Exploration of nature's chemo diversity: The role of secondary metabolites as leads in drug development. *Drug Discovery Today*, 3(5), 232–238.

35. Abiodun Falodun, Obiora Ifesinachi Okafor, Osayemwenre Erharuyi*, O. T. O. (2025). Tropical Journal of Phytochemistry & Pharmaceutical Sciences Available online at <https://www.tjpps.org> Original Research Article Evaluation of Locally Produced Ready to Use Therapeutic Food (RUTF) for Prevention of Childhood Malnutrition. 4(March), 136–140.
36. Keerthiga, T., Tamilarasu, S., & Thamizhiniyan, P. (2025). Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *Hydrocotyle umbellata* L . and its antibacterial properties. 14(4), 154–165.
37. Rudhra, Narayanan, K., & Ravindran, K. (2024). Phytochemical Analysis of Antibacterial activity and FT-IR analysis of leaf extract of *Justicia betonica* L. 18(1001), 984–996. <https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11035982>.

HOW TO CITE: S. Aarthi, P. Thamizhiniyan, S. Tamilarasu, K. Gnanamoorthy, G. Subasree, Phytochemical Analysis and In Vitro Antioxidant Activities of Ethanolic Extract of *Acalypha indica* L., J. Pharm. Sci., 2025, 1 (11), 642-652. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17605182>

